

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF DADRU KUSHTA-CASE REPORT***¹Dhanshri Paikrao, ²Jyoti Meghdambar, ³Santosh Girbide*****¹PG Scholar, ²Professor, ³HOD and Professor,*****Department of Roga Nidan Evam Vikruti Vignyan R.A. Podar Medical College (Ayu) Near Annie Basant Road, Worli. Mumbai India.**

Article Received on 02 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 22 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17746320>

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How to cite this Article: *1Dhanshri Paikrao, 2Jyoti Meghdambar, 3Santosh Girbide. (2025) AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF DADRU KUSHTA-CASE REPORT. "World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(23), 805–814.

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ABSTRACT

Beauty is the desire of every person to please the senses. Ayurveda emphasizes both external and internal beauty, suggesting that external beauty is supported by internal beauty. The skin reflects a person's inner health and outer appearance. Skin health is crucial not just for looks, but also because the skin performs many vital functions for our body and is a strong indicator of health. Nowadays, there has been a significant rise in skin diseases. Most of these diseases are caused by bacterial or fungal infections. Tinea is a superficial fungal infection that accounts for about 5-10% of all skin diseases. According to Ayurveda, all skin diseases fall under the category of 'Kushtha Roga'. In Ayurveda, skin fungal infection is known as Dadru kushtha. Acharya Vagbhata and Sushruta have discussed Dadru Kushtha under Mahakushtha. Acharya Charaka has classified Dadru in Kshudra Kushtha. In this study, a 52-year-old female patient with Dadru kushtha was treated with Ayurvedic medicines along with some dietary changes, such as Khadir

arishtha, Mahattkta ghruta, and Nimda soap. After a few weeks of treatment, significant improvements were seen in symptoms like kandu (itching), daha (burning sensation), rookshata (dryness), and raag (redness).

KEYWORDS: Kushtha roga, Dadru kushtha, Tinea, Fungal infections, ayurved.

INTRODUCTION

Skin problems have been found to be significantly more common in tropical and underdeveloped countries like India¹. In Ayurveda, all skin conditions fall under the broad category of "Kushta," which is further subdivided into Mahakushta and Kshudrakushta. One of the Kushta kinds is Dadru. While Acharya Sushruta^[4] characterises it as a kaphaja ailment that belongs to the Mahakushtha group and affects the tamra (fourth layer) and vedini (fifth layer) of the skin, Acharya Charaka characterises it as a kapha-pittaja vyadhi that falls under the category of Kshudra-kushtha. Raga (erythema), Kandu (itching), Pidika (papules), and Utsanna Mandala (elevated circular lesions) are some of the clinical signs of Dadru Kushtha.^[5]

Its itching sensation is attributed to kapha dosha, papules & erythema is attributed to pitta dosha. Varna (color) are described as red, dark brown & wide spread according to Acharya Charaka, Sushruta & Vagbhata respectively. Acharya Sushruta describes the color of the lesions in dadru more specifically like that of copper or the flower of Atasi and mentions that its pidaka are in the form of parimandala having spreading nature (visarpanshila) but slow in progress or chronic in nature (chirrottham) with kandu.^[6] Dadru is kapha dominant vyadhi. It mainly involves Rasavaha and Raktavaha Srotas. The treatment should be on the principles of Raktavaha srota-dushti.

Dadru's clinical manifestation is comparable to ringworm (tinea infections) in Tinea is one of the several microorganisms that are mostly responsible for skin disorders. A specific class of fungus is responsible for tinea/ringworm infections.

In modern medicine, corticosteroids and topical or systemic antifungals are used to treat tinea. Strong medications can have unfavourable side effects as headache, dizziness, nausea, vomiting, or stomach pain.^[11] These factors make a treatment with a high level of efficacy and no adverse profile necessary. In light of this, this case study was carried out using Ayurveda and Ringworm (Tinea) as Dadru kushtha.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study place- r.a podar ayurved medical college, worli Mumbai.

Local examination

On examination, there is dryness present, there are a large erythematous and infiltrated annular patches with welldefined irregularly marked margins on the face, chest, abdomen No history of any other systemic disease noted.

Ayurvedic Perspective: In Ayurveda, we can associate this clinical entity with dadru kustha based on illness pathology and signs and symptoms. Clinical signs such as Raga (erythema), Kandu (itching), rookshata dryness, Pidika (papule), daha (burning feeling), and Utsanna Mandala (elevated circular lesions) can be used to identify it.^[7] Every Kushtha is a Tridoshaja.^[8] However, Acharya Sushruta Dadru claims that it is Kapha Pradhan,^[9] while Charaka and Vagbhata claim that it is Pitta-Kapha dominance.^[10,11] Acharya Sushruta notes that the pidaka of dadru are in the form of parimandala with a spreading nature (visarpanshila) but a sluggish progression or chronic nature (chirrottham) with kandu. He also compares the colour of the lesions in dadru to that of copper or the flower of Atasi.

Personal History

Name -	xyz
Age -	52 yr
Gender-	female
Occupation-	housewife
Addiction-	none
Appetite-	regular
Bladder-	regular
Marital status -	married
Diet -	non vegetarian
Sleep-	inadequate due to itching,burning
Bowel-	irregular

General examination

Height	150 Cm
Weight	63
Bmi	28KG/M2
B.P	110/80 Mm Hg
Tempreture	Afebrile
Pulse Rate	80/Min
Respiratory Rate	20/Min
Pallor	Not Present
Pedal Edema	Not Present
Icterus	Not Present
Lymphadenopathy	Not Present
Clubbing	Not Present
Cynosis	Not Present

Ashtavidh Pariksha

Nadi – Pitta-Kaphaja	Mala – Baddha
Mutra - Prakruta	Jivha – Ishat Saam
Shabda - Spashta	Sparsha – Prakruta
Druk -Prakruta	Aakruti - Madhyam

Dashvidha pariksaha

Pakriti -	Vaat-kafa
Vikriti -	Prakriti sam samveta
Sara -	madhyam
Samhanan -	madhyam
Pramana -	madhyam
Satmya -	madhyam
Satva -	madhyam
Vyama shakti -	madhyam
Jarana shakti -	madhyam
Vaya -	madhyam

Treatment

1. Khadir+Nimba+Triphala Kadha – 20 MI Twice A Day Before Meal
2. Khadiraarishtha – 15 MI Twice A Day After Meal
3. Mauktik Yukta Kamdudha – After Meal Thrice A Day
4. Shatadhauth Ghruta- For LA Twice Aday
5. Aarogyavardhini Vati – 2 Vati Twice Aday After Meal
6. Gandharva Haritaki – 1tbl Spoon After Meal At Night
7. Mahatitka Ghruta – 5ml Twice A Day After Meal

Follow up – assessment of the skin was done on first visit and patient follow up at the interval of 15-20 days was done up till complete remission of clinical symptoms. During the treatment and follow up patient is advised to avoid incompatible food items, junk/fast food, non-veg, oily spicy food, sea food (fish) and patient is advised to avoid day.

Before treatment**Figure 3****DISSCUSSION**

The goal of the current study was to identify a safe and efficient way to treat Dadru. Dadru is a Kapha-pittaja Vyadhi, hence a recipe with Kapha-pitta shaamaka qualities should be chosen to manage it. The treatment should be based on the concepts of Raktavaha srota-dushti since

it incorporates both rasavaha and raktavaha srotas. Raga (erythema), Kandu (itching), rookshata (dryness), and daha (burning sensation) have been significantly improved in this case study. Significant improvements in bowel habits and appetite have also been noted during the research. The intrinsic characteristics of the medication can be used to comprehend its mode of action.

1. Arogya vardhini vati – It Is Used In The Liver Disorders And Balances Pitta, It Is Widely Used In Skin Disease Such As Hyper-Pigmentation, Acne Etc Probable Mode Of Action Of Arogyavardhini Vati Arogyavardhini Vati Is A Herbomineral Formulation Mainly Indicated In Kushta Roga. The Main Ingredient Of Arogyavardhini Vati Is Kutaki (Picrorrhizakurroa Royle Ex Benth). It Also Contains Haritaki (Terminalia Chebula Retz.), Bibhitaka (Terminalia Bellerica (Gaertn.) Roxb.), Amalaki (Emblca Officinalis Gaertn), Shilajatu Shuddha (Asphaltum), Guggulu Shuddha (Commiphora Wightii Arn.), Eranda (Ricinus Communis Linn.), And Minerals Like Shuddha Parada (Purified Mercury), Shuddha Gandhaka (Purified Sulfur), Lauha Bhasma (Iron Compound In Ash Form), Abhraka Bhasma (Mica In Ash Form), And Tamra Bhasma (Copper Compounds In Ash Form) With Bhavana Of Nimba (Azadirachta Indica A.Juss) Patra Swarasa. Due To All These Ingredients, It Possesses Pitta Virechan, Tridosha Shamak, Deepan, Pachan, Kushthaghna, And Kandughna Properties. Due To These Properties It Helps In Balancing Tridosha, Causes Agnivardhana, Bhedana, malashodhana and vatanulomana.^[12] Kushtaghna and Kandughna properties help in relieving symptoms and breaking samprapti of disease.

2. Shata dhauta ghrita -Shatdhaut Ghrita has a number of key properties that make it beneficial for skin care. Its traditional use in Ayurvedic medicine was specifically for skin healing, hydration, and anti-aging. Shatdhaut Ghrita, due to its lipid-rich nature, acts as an excellent emollient. It deeply penetrates the skin's stratum corneum (the outermost skin layer), providing intense moisture without causing a greasy or oily residue. This makes it an excellent choice for individuals with dry skin, as it can lock moisture into the skin for hours. The moisture retention helps maintain skin hydration, preventing dryness.^[13] Shatdhaut Ghrita, due to its lipid-rich nature, acts as an excellent emollient. It deeply penetrates the skin's stratum corneum (the outermost skin layer), providing intense moisture without causing a greasy or oily residue. This makes it an excellent choice for individuals with dry skin, as it can lock moisture into the skin for hours. The moisture retention helps maintain skin hydration, preventing dryness. Antioxidant and Anti-Aging Properties: Non-

Comedogenic Nature: Deep Hydration and Moisturization. In classical Ayurvedic texts, ghee (clarified butter) is described as an essential nutrient for the skin, especially for its moisturizing and rejuvenating properties. According to the Charaka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita, ghee is beneficial for nourishing and hydrating tissues, especially when applied externally.^[14]

3. Mahatikta ghruta -is the best drug for *Kushta*. The main ingredient of this is *Amalaki* that prevents relapse of symptoms. It prevents drying of the skin and akes the skin soft. According to Ayurveda, it pacifies *vata dosha* that is the main doshas of psoriasis.^[15] Mahatikta ghruta: Mahatikta ghruta have a large number of herbs which are bitter in taste. Tikta rasa help in balancing of Pitta dosha. On the other hand, Ghruta itself mitigates pitta dosha. It acts mainly on Kled, Meda, Lasika, Rakta, Pitta and Kapha which helps in balancing the vitiated dosha and dhatu. It acts as Raktasodhak, Kushtaghna, Kandughna, Varnya.^[16]

4. Khadirarista: Main ingredients of Khadirarista is Khadira which is Krimigna And Kandugna with Kapha-pitta samakaproperties. It is helpful in subsiding the symptoms of itching, rashes and sensitivity.

5. Gandharva haritaki -is vatanuloman, purish mala shodhan.^[17]

6. Khadira- highly esteemed as Kushthaghna, a single-use drug for treating all types of skin disorders through both internal and external applications. It is widely used for managing conditions like acne, eczema, psoriasis, and other inflammatory skin conditions.^[18,19]

7. Nimba -properties as per AyurvedicliteratureAs per ayurvedic literature Nimba Rasa (Taste) is Tikta, Kashaya, Guna (Qualities) are Laghu, Ruksha, Veerya (Potency) is Sheeta, Vipaka (Post-digesion effect) is Katu and Karma (Pharmacological activity) are Kaphaghna, Pittaghna karma. Nimbapatra is shothghna, twagadosahar, krimighna, kushthahar, vranashodhak and vranaropak. Nimbatwak is graahi, jwaraghna, twagadosahar & krimighna. Nimba fruit is kushtha, Gulma, krimi & pramehanashak, Nimba tail is vranashodhak, vranaropak, vaathar, kushthaghna & krimighna.^[20]

8. Triphala- Antioxidant Protection: Triphala neutralizes these harmful particles and keeps your skin ever-young and glowing. Anti-Inflammatory Effects: Herbs present in Triphala exert anti-inflammatory actions, hence soothing irritated skin and reducing its redness. This proves to be most useful for conditions like acne and eczema. Detoxification: Triphala

enhances the natural detoxification processes of the body. Its regular intake will help clear out all the toxins from your system, which, in turn, usually reflect in the skin, making it clearer and more vibrant. 3. Skin Elasticity- Amalaki, one of the basic constituents of Triphala, is rich in vitamin C, which boosts collagen production in your body. Collagen thus produced is a requisite for the elasticity and firmness of the skin, hence smoothly gliding your skin to its youthfulness.

4. Balances Skin Tone: The herb helps to balance out your skin tone by eliminating hyperpigmentation. Its natural characteristics ensure glowing skin, fading away dark spots and blemishes.

9. Kamdudha Moti Yukt -an Ayurvedic herbo-mineral tablet containing ingredients like pearl and coral that is used to manage various ailments including hyperacidity, heartburn, and digestive issues.

CONCLUSION

Although dadru is thought to be treatable, it is naturally quite persistent. It is important to seek suitable treatment as soon as possible because remissions and relapses are prevalent if the treatment process is not controlled appropriately. With this case study, we hope to demonstrate the significant potential of the Ayurvedic therapeutic method for dadru kustha. Corticosteroids and topical or systemic antifungal medications are used in modern medicine to treat tinea. These drugs are often strong, and using them might cause a number of unfavourable side effects, such as headache, lightheadedness, nausea, vomiting, or stomach pain. Although dadru is thought to be treatable, it is naturally quite persistent. If the course of treatment is not carefully monitored, Remissions and relapses are common, therefore it's critical to get the right treatment as soon as possible. With this case study, we hope to demonstrate the significant potential of the Ayurvedic therapeutic method for dadru kustha. Corticosteroids and topical or systemic antifungal medications are used in modern medicine to treat tinea. These drugs are often strong, and using them might cause a number of unfavourable side effects, such as headache, lightheadedness, nausea, vomiting, or stomach pain.

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